

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for Glucocorticoid receptor (UniProt ID: P04150) for use in western blot and flow cytometry

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Abstract

Inhaled corticosteroids are the cornerstone of asthma therapy, reducing airway inflammation, mucus hypersecretion, and bronchial hyperresponsiveness. These effects are mediated by the glucocorticoid receptor (NR3C1), which regulates anti-inflammatory gene transcription following activation. However, approximately 10% of patients are corticosteroid-refractory, highlighting the need for robust antibodies to accurately study receptor expression, localisation, and function. Here we systematically characterised twenty-two commercial antibodies for western blot and flow cytometry using a standardized knockout validation approach in human A549 cells, comparing readouts in a *NR3C1* knockout line with its isogenic parental controls. These experiments form part of a broader collaborative initiative to address antibody reproducibility by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins and making the results openly available to the community. While antibody use and protocol conditions vary between laboratories, this report provides a resource to guide the selection of suitable reagents for studies of the glucocorticoid receptor in health and disease.

Keywords

P04150, NR3C1, glucocorticoid receptor, antibody validation, western blot, flow cytometry, asthma, corticosteroids, glucocorticoids.

Introduction

Inhaled corticosteroids are the cornerstone therapy for asthma treatment and have been demonstrated to improve asthma control through the reduction of mucus hypersecretion, airway inflammation, and bronchial hyperresponsiveness (1). These therapeutic effects are achieved through activation of the glucocorticoid receptor (*NR3C1*), a ligand-activated transcription factor that mediates the anti-inflammatory actions of corticosteroids. Upon corticosteroid binding, glucocorticoid receptor chaperone proteins dissociate, facilitating receptor translocation to the nucleus where it binds glucocorticoid response elements to regulate gene transcription (2). Consequently, there is now an in-depth understanding of the canonical function of the glucocorticoid receptor. However, approximately 10% of patients with asthma are refractory to corticosteroid therapy, resulting in increased morbidity and mortality (3). The underlying molecular mechanisms driving this resistance include abnormalities in glucocorticoid receptor signalling, with receptor function also potentially modulated by the presence of novel splice variants (4). Reliable antibodies are therefore required to accurately characterise glucocorticoid receptor expression, localisation, and function in asthma research.

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterising commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols (5) and openly sharing the data (6). Here we evaluated the performance of twenty-two commercial glucocorticoid receptor antibodies for use in western blot and flow cytometry, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of glucocorticoid receptor function and properties. The platform for antibody characterisation used to carry out this study was endorsed by a committee of industry academic representatives. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterisation procedures using most commercially available renewable antibodies against the corresponding protein. The standardised consensus antibody characterisation protocols are openly available on Protocols.io (DOI: [dx.doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)).

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterisation data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret the antibody characterisation data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (7).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from WT (wild type) and KO cells (8-10). The first step is to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcript per million “TPM” + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655). The cell line A549 expresses the *NR3C1* transcript at $5.4 \log_2$ (TPM+1) and thus was identified as a suitable cell line and was modified by CRISPR/Cas9 to KO the corresponding *NR3C1* gene (Table 1).

For western blot experiments, WT and *NR3C1* KO protein lysates were run on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes and probed in parallel with twenty-two glucocorticoid receptor antibodies (Figure 1).

For flow cytometry, A549 WT and *NR3C1* KO cells were labelled with distinct fluorescent dyes and combined at a 1:1 ratio. Both cell lines were fixed, permeabilised and blocked in the same tube prior to antibody staining to reduce bias. Twenty-two glucocorticoid receptor antibodies were then evaluated, with fluorescent intensity assessed using the Attune NxT flow cytometer. Antibody staining in both WT and KO line was then quantified using FlowJo software, with representative histograms presented in Figure 2.

In conclusion, we have screened twenty-two commercial glucocorticoid receptor antibodies by western blot and flow cytometry by comparing the signal produced using human A549 WT and *NR3C1* KO cells. High-quality and renewable antibodies capable of successfully detecting the glucocorticoid receptor were identified in all applications.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does

not test all commercially available glucocorticoid receptor antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners. We encourage readers to consult vendor documentation to identify the specific antigen each antibody is raised against, where such information is available.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in studying the glucocorticoid receptor, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. Experts are invited to analyse and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots. Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Methods

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io (DOI: [dx.doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)).

Antibodies

All glucocorticoid receptor antibodies are listed in Table 2, together with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRID), to ensure antibodies are cited properly (11). Secondary antibodies used in this study are provided in Table 3. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations.

Cell culture

All cell lines used in this study are listed in Table 1, alongside their corresponding RRIDs, to ensure proper citation (12). Cells were cultured in DMEM high-glucose (Capricorn Scientific #DMEM-HPSTA) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (Thermo Fisher Scientific #A5256801) and 1% antibiotic/antimycotic solution (Capricorn Scientific #AAS-B). All cell lines used in this study were routinely tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing

The A549 *NR3C1* KO clone was generated using low-passage cells. Prior to ribonucleoprotein transfection, 20,000 cells were plated in each well of a 48-well plate and incubated overnight to allow attachment. In vitro guide RNA was generated with the HighYield T7 sgRNA synthesis kit (Jena Bioscience #RNT-105), followed by incubation with DNase I-XT (New England Biolabs #M0570) and quick CIP (New England Biolabs #M0525) to remove DNA and 5' phosphorylation respectively. RNA was purified using the Monarch spin RNA cleanup kit (New England Biolabs #T2040) and 125ng of guide RNA (target sequence: AAGCTTCATCAGAGCACACC) was combined with 625ng of spCas9. Ribonucleoprotein transfection was then carried out using the Lipofectamine CRISPRMAX Cas9 transfection reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific #CMAX000008) according to the manufacturer's protocol. The culture medium was replaced the following day, and single-cell isolation was performed on day three. Single cells were plated into 96-well plates and clonally expanded.

Antibody screening by western blot

For lysate preparation, A549 WT and *NR3C1* KO cells were washed three times in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific #70011044) and lysed in RIPA buffer containing 1x of protease inhibitor cocktail, sodium orthovanadate and phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (Santa Cruz Biotechnology #sc-24948). Lysates were sonicated (40% amplitude for 5 seconds) three times and incubated for 30 minutes on ice prior to centrifugation at 20,000 x g for 1 hour at 4°C.

Protein concentration was confirmed using the Pierce BCA protein assay (Thermo Fisher Scientific #23225) and 30µg of protein was used. Samples were combined with Laemmli sample buffer (Bio-Rad #1610747) containing 2-mercaptoethanol (final concentration 35mM) (Sigma Aldrich #M7522) before being heated at 65°C for 10 minutes. Samples were then loaded in precast 4-20% WedgeWell Tris-Glycine Plus midi gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific #WTG42020BOX) alongside Prime-Step prestained broad range protein ladder (BioLegend #773302). SDS-PAGE was then performed in SureLock Tandem Midi Gel tanks (Thermo Fisher Scientific #STM1001) and run at 200V for 1 hour with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad #1610772). Proteins were then transferred to 0.2µm supported nitrocellulose membranes (Cytiva #10600015) using a Criterion blotter with plate electrodes (Bio-Rad #17004070) run at 85V for 45 minutes. Proteins on the blot were visualised with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific #161470250) which was scanned to show alongside individual western blots. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hour except for antibody 12041 which was blocked in 5% BSA in Tris-buffered saline containing 1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Thermo Fisher Scientific #J77500.K2). Primary antibodies were then incubated overnight at 4°C in 5% milk TBST with gentle shaking. Following three ten-minute washes with TBST, horseradish peroxidase (HRP) conjugated secondary antibodies were incubated at a dilution of 1/10000 (0.1µg/mL) in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hour at room temperature followed by three ten-minute washes with TBST. Membranes were then incubated with either Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific #32106) for 1 minute or Clarity Western ECL substrate (Bio-Rad #1705061) for 5 minutes prior to detection with the ImageQuant LAS 4000.

Antibody screening by flow cytometry

A549 WT and *NR3C1* KO cells were detached, and ten million cells were labelled with CellTracker green or violet fluorescent dyes, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, #C7025 and #C10094). WT and KO cells were centrifuged at 300 x g, for 10 minutes and resuspended in PBS containing 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA) (Sigma-Aldrich, A9647). The two populations were combined at a 1:1 ratio, centrifuged and fixed on ice for 20 minutes using 800 µL of 4% PFA in PBS (Thermo Fisher Scientific #J19943.K2) unless otherwise stated.

Following fixation, 1.2 mL of 1% BSA in PBS was added to the tube, vortexed and centrifuged at 600 x *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then permeabilised in 400 µL PBS with 0.1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, J63521.AP) for 10 min at room temperature. Following permeabilisation, 1 mL of 1% BSA PBS was added to the tube, centrifuged at 600 x *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C and then blocked with 5% goat serum (Sigma-Aldrich #G6767), 1% BSA in PBS for 30 minutes on ice. After the blocking step 400,000 cells were aliquoted into individually labelled tubes, centrifuged at 600 x *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C and incubated in 150 µL of 1% BSA PBS with primary glucocorticoid receptor antibodies for 30 minutes on ice. 500 µL of 1% BSA PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged at 600 x *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then incubated with their corresponding secondary antibodies (Table 3) in 150 µL of 1% BSA PBS for 30 minutes on ice. 500 µL of 1% BSA PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged 600 x *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then resuspended in 1 ml of 1% BSA in PBS and data was acquired using the Attune NxT flow cytometer.

Data was analysed using FlowJo. Cells were first gated on the FSC-A vs SSC-A, followed by single-cell discrimination using FSC-A vs FSC-H. WT and KO populations were then separated on the BL1-A vs VL1-A using a quadrant gate. Quantification of antibody staining was then observed in the RL1-A channel and histograms merged to demonstrate the staining intensity between the two populations compared to the two secondary only controls. Figures were then assembled using Adobe Illustrator 2024.

Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: Dataset for the glucocorticoid receptor antibody screening study <DOI>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1. Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalogue number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	ab288558	CVCL_0023	A549	WT
University of Leicester	-	CVCL_FORK	A549	NR3C1 KO

Table 2. Summary of the glucocorticoid receptor antibodies tested.

Company	Catalogue number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Stock concentration (µg/mL)	Vendor recommended applications
Abcam	ab183127**	1023477-26	AB_2833234	Monoclonal Recombinant	EPR19621	Rabbit	549	FC, ICC/IF, IHC, WB
Abcam	ab302677**	1031859-2	AB_3668813	Monoclonal Recombinant	41-Glucocorticoid Receptor	Mouse	899	ICC/IF, IHC, WB
Abcam	ab305050**	1017258-3	AB_3668815	Monoclonal Recombinant	EPR24889-231	Rabbit	512	ICC/IF, IHC, IP, WB
Abcam	ab307605**	1097748-1	AB_3668816	Monoclonal Recombinant	2153CT307.3 2.80	Mouse	1026	WB
Abclonal	A19583**	4000000062	AB_2862682	Monoclonal Recombinant	ARC0062	Rabbit	250	ELISA, IP, WB
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP31090_P050	QC0765-40668	AB_10885477	Polyclonal	-	Rabbit	500	IHC, WB
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP45593_P050	QC13871-231019	AB_2046941	Polyclonal	-	Rabbit	500	IHC, WB
Aviva Systems Biology	P100765_P050	QC0765	AB_10715829	Polyclonal	-	Rabbit	500	WB
Cell Signalling Technology	12041**	5	AB_2631286	Monoclonal Recombinant	D6H2L	Rabbit	98	FC, ICC/IF, IHC, IP, WB
Cell Signalling Technology	3660**	5	AB_11179215	Monoclonal Recombinant	D8H2	Rabbit	294	FC, ICC/IF, IP, WB
GeneTex	GTX101120	39834	AB_1951023	Polyclonal	-	Rabbit	1000	ICC/IF, IHC, IP, WB
GeneTex	GTX113208	43803	AB_10721056	Polyclonal	-	Rabbit	380	ICC/IF, IHC, IP, WB
GeneTex	GTX634647*	43276	AB_2888468	Monoclonal	GT248	Mouse	1970	IHC, WB

GeneTex	GTX634705*	43283	AB_2888473	Monoclonal	GT1073	Mouse	2210	IHC, WB
GeneTex	GTX636420**	44452	AB_2909980	Monoclonal Recombinant	HL1149	Rabbit	1000	ICC/IF, IHC, WB
GeneTex	GTX636422**	44452	AB_2909981	Monoclonal Recombinant	HL1151	Rabbit	1000	ICC/IF, IHC, WB
Proteintech	24050-1-AP	105483	AB_2813890	Polyclonal	-	Rabbit	850	ELISA, ICC/IF, IHC, IP, WB
Proteintech	82619-1-RR**	23005153	AB_3086492	Monoclonal Recombinant	2F22	Rabbit	1000	ELISA, ICC/IF, IHC, IP, WB
Bio-Techne	MAB10144*	1006903	AB_10903120	Monoclonal	1006903	Mouse	500	ICC/IF, IHC, WB
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA1-510*	ZC395194	AB_325427	Monoclonal	BuGR2	Mouse	1000	FC, ICC/IF, IHC, IP, WB
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-15801*	ZF4351935B	AB_11152837	Monoclonal	6E6	Mouse	-	ELISA, FC, ICC/IF, IHC, WB
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-35309**	ZF4352647	AB_2849211	Monoclonal Recombinant	ARC0062	Rabbit	200	IP, WB

* Monoclonal antibody, ** Recombinant antibody.

ELISA = Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, FC = Flow cytometry, ICC/IF = Immunocytochemistry/ immunofluorescence, IHC = immunohistochemistry, IP = immunoprecipitation, WB = Western blot.

Table 3. Summary of the secondary antibodies used.

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalogue number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Application	Stock concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	Working concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	Recombinant Polyclonal	Western blot	1000	0.1
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	Recombinant Polyclonal	Western blot	1000	0.1
Proteintech	Coralite-Plus-647-Goat Anti-Rabbit (H + L)	RGAR005	AB_3073509	Recombinant Polyclonal	Flow cytometry	500	0.625
Proteintech	Coralite-Plus-647-Goat Anti-Mouse (H + L)	RGAM005	AB_3073503	Recombinant Polyclonal	Flow cytometry	500	0.625

Figure 1: Glucocorticoid receptor antibody screening by immunoblot

Figure 2: Glucocorticoid receptor antibody screening by flow cytometry

Figure legends

Figure 1: Glucocorticoid receptor antibody screening by western blot using protein lysates

Protein lysates from A549 WT and *NR3C1* KO cells were collected, and 30µg of protein was used for western blot with the indicated glucocorticoid receptor antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO samples. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab183127** at 1/2000, ab302677** at 1/1000, ab305050** at 1/1000, ab307605** at 1/1000, A19583** at 1/1000, ARP31090_P050 at 1/500, ARP45593_P050 at 1/500, P100765_P050 at 1/500, 12041** at 1/1000, 3660** at 1/1000, GTX101120 at 1/1000, GTX113208 at 1/1000, GTX634647* at 1/1000, GTX634705* at 1/1000, GTX636420** at 1/1000, GTX636422** at 1/1000, 24050-1-AP at 1/5000, 82619-1-RR** at 1/5000, MAB10144* at 1/250, MA1-510* at 1/200, MA5-15801* at 1/500, and MA5-35309** at 1/500. Predicted band size: 85.7kDa. ** = recombinant antibody, * = monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: Glucocorticoid receptor antibody screening by flow cytometry (PFA-Triton X-100)

A549 WT and *NR3C1* KO cells were labelled with a green or violet, fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed in a 1:1 ratio, fixed in 4% PFA and permeabilized in 0.1% Triton X-100. 400,000 cells were stained with the indicated glucocorticoid receptor antibodies and corresponding Multi-rAb Coralite® Plus 647 secondary antibodies. Antibody staining was quantified using the Attune NxT Flow Cytometer with representative images showing the staining intensity in the KO population (pink histogram, dashed line) compared to the WT cells (green histogram, solid line). Histograms with dotted lines represent secondary antibody-only controls in both WT and KO cells. Antibody dilutions used: ab183127** at 1/5490, ab302677** at 1/8990, ab305050** at 1/5120, ab307605** at 1/10260, A19583** at 1/2500, ARP31090_P050 at 1/5000, ARP45593_P050 at 1/5000, P100765_P050 at 1/5000, 12041** at 1/980, 3660** at 1/6400, GTX101120 at 1/10000, GTX113208 at 1/3800, GTX634647* at 1/19700, GTX634705* at 1/22100, GTX636420** at 1/10000, GTX636422** at 1/10000, 24050-1-AP at 1/8500, 82619-1-RR** at 1/10000, MAB10144* at 1/500, MA1-510* at 1/1000, MA5-15801* at 1/400, and MA5-35309** at 1/2000. ** = recombinant antibody, * = monoclonal antibody.